

Electronic Supplementary Information

Photoluminescence and Raman study of the high-pressure behavior of monoclinic $(\text{Eu}_{1-x}\text{Yb}_x)_2\text{O}_3$ solid solutions

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1. XRD analysis. Rietveld refinements. Structural data.

Fig. S1. Rietveld refinement of the room temperature XRD patterns of $(\text{Eu}_{1-x}\text{Yb}_x)_2\text{O}_3$ solid solutions with compositions $x = 0$ (a), 0.1 (b), 0.15 (c) and 0.2 (d). Lattice parameters and R -factors indicating the quality of the fit are also included within the plot.

Table 1. Fractional coordinates (x, y, z) of Eu_2O_3 after Rietveld refinement. Only those of the RE ions were refined.

Atom	x	y	z
Eu1	0.1346(6)	0.5	0.4909(6)
Eu2	0.1912(7)	0.5	0.1384(8)
Eu3	0.4698(10)	0.5	0.1852(10)
O1	0.1291	0	0.2855
O2	0.3248	0.5	0.0267
O3	0.2961	0.5	0.3732
O4	0.4734	0	0.3431
O5	0	0.5	0

Table 2. Fractional coordinates (x,y,z) of $\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Yb}$ 10% after Rietveld refinement. Only those of the RE ions were refined.

Atom	x	y	z
Eu1/Yb1	0.1332(5)	0.5	0.4908(5)
Eu2/Yb2	0.1896(5)	0.5	0.1371(7)
Eu3/Yb3	0.4684(7)	0.5	0.1861(9)
O1	0.1291	0	0.2855
O2	0.3248	0.5	0.0267
O3	0.2961	0.5	0.3732
O4	0.4734	0	0.3431
O5	0	0.5	0

Table 3. Fractional coordinates (x,y,z) of $\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Yb}$ 15% after Rietveld refinement. Only those of the RE ions were refined.

Atom	x	y	z
Eu1/Yb1	0.1342(3)	0.5	0.4919(3)
Eu2/Yb2	0.1905(5)	0.5	0.1375(4)
Eu3/Yb3	0.4687(7)	0.5	0.1853(5)
O1	0.1291	0	0.2855
O2	0.3248	0.5	0.0267
O3	0.2961	0.5	0.3732
O4	0.4734	0	0.3431
O5	0	0.5	0

Table 4. Fractional coordinates (x,y,z) of $\text{Eu}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Yb}$ 20% after Rietveld refinement. Only those of the RE ions were refined.

Atom	x	y	z
Eu1/Yb1	0.1345(3)	0.5	0.4907(4)
Eu2/Yb2	0.1915(4)	0.5	0.1370(5)
Eu3/Yb3	0.4689(5)	0.5	0.1860(6)
O1	0.1291	0	0.2855
O2	0.3248	0.5	0.0267
O3	0.2961	0.5	0.3732
O4	0.4734	0	0.3431
O5	0	0.5	0

2. XRF measurements

XRF measurements were performed in a Bruker D2-Phaser diffractometer equipped with an X-flash detector. Spectra 7 software was employed for the qualitative and quantitative spectra analysis on the $(\text{Eu}_{1-x}\text{Yb}_x)_2\text{O}_3$ solid solution. XRF fluorescence spectra were reconstructed using only Eu and Yb contributions (see Fig. S2).

Fig. S2. XRF results on the $(\text{Eu}_{0.85}\text{Yb}_{0.15})_2\text{O}_3$ sample. The red line corresponds to the experimental spectrum whereas the blue line indicates the reconstructed one. Only Eu and Yb contributions account for the observed spectra. No other RE contributions were detected in the explored range.

Based on this analysis, roughly estimating the elemental composition of Yb and Eu on the three samples was possible. Thus, Yb composition was determined from the relative intensities of L1 contributions: Eu (5.85 keV) and Yb (7.42 keV). Previously, calibration was performed from weighted mixtures of Yb_2O_3 and Eu_2O_3 (Yb content: $x = 0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3$). Table 5 summarizes the results on the series studied in this work.

Table 5. Results of the XRF elemental analysis on the $(\text{Eu}_{1-x}\text{Yb}_x)_2\text{O}_3$ studied samples.

Sample	Yb nominal composition (%)	Yb composition from XRF (%)
$(\text{Eu}_{0.9}\text{Yb}_{0.1})_2\text{O}_3$	10	10(1)
$(\text{Eu}_{0.85}\text{Yb}_{0.15})_2\text{O}_3$	15	13(1)
$(\text{Eu}_{0.8}\text{Yb}_{0.2})_2\text{O}_3$	20	19(1)